

A Retrospective Study to Estimate Prevalence and Severity of DR and in Newly Diagnosed Type 2 DM Patients

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Aim: The aim of the present study was to estimate prevalence and severity of DR and in recently diagnosed type 2 DM patients.

Material & Methods: A study was conducted in the Department of Ophthalmology, Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India from February 2017 to January 2018. This observational, prospective study was conducted in patients who visited the diabetic clinic and recently diagnosed (less than 3 months from first diagnosis) for type 2 DM. In present study total 100 patients were evaluated for diabetic retinopathy.

Results: In present study total 100 patients were evaluated for diabetic retinopathy. Most of patients were from 61-70 years (25%), followed by 51-60 years (22%) and 41-50 years (20%) age group. Male patients (58%) were more than female patients (42%). We noted 10% prevalence of diabetic retinopathy in study patients. Prevalence was more in males (66.66%) as compared to females (33.33%). In present study diabetic retinopathy was noted in 15 patients, divided as mild no proliferative diabetic retinopathy (66.66%), Moderate no proliferative diabetic retinopathy (20%), Severe no proliferative diabetic retinopathy (6.66%) and proliferative diabetic retinopathy (PDR) (6.66%). Macular oedema was noted in 4 patients. 60% of them had mild macular oedema while 20% each had moderate and severe macular oedema.

Conclusion: Screening for diabetic retinopathy is important for newly diagnosed diabetic patients. A systematic screening program in the community is needed for early detection and to reduce blindness in diabetic patients.

Keywords: Diabetic Retinopathy, Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, Non-proliferative, Macular Oedema

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Introduction

Diabetic retinopathy (DR) is the leading cause of visual impairment in the Western world, particularly among persons of working age. [1,2] It is estimated that DR develops in more than 75% of diabetic patients within 15 to 20 years of diagnosis of diabetes. [3,4] Several epidemiologic studies have provided valuable information on the prevalence of DR in Western countries that is useful for identifying subgroups at risk and for the planning of public health policies. [5] The Eye Diseases Prevalence Research Group collates data on eye diseases in the United States, and provides information on the health services burden due to eye diseases, including DR. [5] However, there is a paucity of data on the prevalence of diabetes-related eye diseases in developing countries such as India, which in fact has the largest number of diabetic individuals in the world.

According to the latest World Health Organization (WHO) report, India has 31.7 million diabetic

subjects, and the number is expected to increase to a staggering 79.4 million by 2030. [6] Furthermore, type 2 diabetes in Indians differs from that in Europeans in several aspects: The onset is at a younger age, [7] obesity is less common, [8] and genetic factors appear to be stronger. [9] These clinical differences and the rising prevalence of diabetes in India [10] warrant well-conducted epidemiologic studies on diabetes-related complications in this population, to assess the health services burden due to diabetes.

Diabetic retinopathy (DR) is the leading cause of visual impairment among working-age adults; however, increasing awareness and the early identification of DM has ameliorated the problem somewhat. [11] Most standard protocols for the screening of DR recommend annual or biannual dilated retinal examinations for all patients with diabetes. [12]

Therefore, in present study we aimed to estimate prevalence and severity of DR and in recently diagnosed type 2 DM patients

Material & Methods

A study was conducted in the Department of Ophthalmology, Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India from February 2017 to January 2018. This retrospective study was conducted in patients who visited the diabetic clinic and recently diagnosed (less than 3 months from first diagnosis) for type 2 DM. In present study total 100 patients were evaluated for diabetic retinopathy.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients who were recently diagnosed (less than 3 months from first diagnosis) for type 2 DM, willing to participate

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients with mature cataracts and hazy media, whose fundi could not be examined.
- Patients with a history of exposure to radiation, hypertensive retinopathy without DM, sickle cell disease and pheochromocytoma.
- Patients who were not willing to participate.

Methodology

Study was explained and a written informed consent was taken. Patients underwent history taking (age, sex, medical history, smoking), general physical examination and routine ophthalmological examination was done. The pupils of both eyes were dilated by using a mydriatic agent (1% Tropicamide eye drops). Distant direct ophthalmoscopy, direct ophthalmoscopy and binocular indirect ophthalmoscopy were done. Binocular indirect ophthalmoscopy was done with a 20 D lens with the patient in supine position. Findings were noted and patients were categorized according to findings; whether diabetic retinopathy was present or absent. If present, retinopathy was classified according to early treatment of diabetic retinopathy study (ETDRS) classification. [13] Presence of diabetic macular oedema was noted. If present, it was further classified into clinically significant (CSME) or non-significant. [13]

Statistical Analysis

Data was collected, entered in Microsoft excel sheet and analysed by descriptive statistics

Results

Table 1: Age and gender distribution

Age in years	Total N=100	Diabetic Retinopathy N=15
≤ 40	10 (10%)	2 (13.33%)
41-50	20 (20%)	2 (13.33%)
51-60	22 (22%)	3 (20%)
61-70	25 (25%)	3 (20%)
71-80	17 (17%)	3 (20%)
>80	6 (6%)	2 (13.33%)
Total	100	15
Gender		
Male	58 (58%)	10 (66.66%)
Female	42 (42%)	5 (33.33%)

In present study total 100 patients were evaluated for diabetic retinopathy. Most of patients were from 61-70 years (25%), followed by 51-60 years (22%) and 41-50 years (20%) age group. Male patients (58%)

were more than female patients (42%). We noted 10% prevalence of diabetic retinopathy in study patients. Prevalence was more in males (66.66%) as compared to females (33.33%).

Table 2: Diabetic retinopathy and macular oedema

Diabetic retinopathy (N=15)	N	%
Mild NPDR	10	66.66
Moderate NPDR	3	20
Severe NPDR	1	6.66
PDR	1	6.66
Total	15	100
Macular edema (N=5)		
Mild	3	60
Moderate	1	20
Severe	1	20

In present study diabetic retinopathy was noted in 15 patients, divided as mild non proliferative diabetic retinopathy (66.66%), Moderate non proliferative diabetic retinopathy (20%), Severe non proliferative diabetic retinopathy (6.66%) and proliferative diabetic retinopathy (PDR) (6.66%). Macular oedema was noted in 4 patients. 60% of them had mild macular oedema while 20% each had moderate and severe macular oedema.

Discussion

Diabetes mellitus (DM) has exemplified its presence globally. In India, 69.1 million are diabetics as of 2015 compared to 18 million in 1995. [14,15] At this rate, crossing one billion as estimated by the International Diabetes Federation Association and World health organization seems obvious. [15] Pan India studies on the prevalence of Diabetic retinopathy (DR) are limited, few initial studies, such as The Chennai Urban Rural Epidemiology Study and Arvind comprehensive eye study in rural population, concluded the prevalence of DR as 17.8% and 10.8% in diabetics, respectively. [16,17] DR is a common microvascular complication, an important complication among adults and elderly. DR is of two types, non proliferative diabetic retinopathy (NPDR) and proliferative diabetic retinopathy (PDR). Severity of NPDR depends on microaneurysms, haemorrhages, cotton wool spots, and beading of veins and can progress to PDR. Inherent characteristic of PDR is neovascularization. Its either PDR or diabetic maculopathy that is responsible for vision loss. Chronic hyperglycaemia inflicts profoundly in development and progression of DR by stimulating multiple mechanisms such as polyol pathway, enzymatic glycation, protein kinase C activation, hemodynamic changes, and renin angiotensin aldosterone pathway [18] and Type 2 DM accounts for more than 90% of the diabetic population worldwide. [19]

Proliferative diabetic retinopathy (PDR) is a treatable cause of severe visual loss in people with diabetes. If left untreated, most eyes with low-risk PDR characterized by mild to moderate retinal or optic disc neovascularization progress to high-risk PDR with increasing retinal or disc neovascularization. Risk factors for the development of retinopathy and visual loss include type of diabetes, duration of diabetes, poor glycaemic control, poor blood pressure control, deranged lipid profile, obesity, obstructive sleep apnoea (OSA), pregnancy and anaemia. The duration of diabetes is probably the strongest predictor for development and progression of retinopathy. [4] In present study total 100 patients were evaluated for diabetic retinopathy. Most of patients were from 61-70 years (25%), followed by 51-60 years (22%) and 41-50 years (20%) age group. Male patients (58%) were more than female patients (42%). We noted 10%

prevalence of diabetic retinopathy in study patients. Prevalence was more in males (66.66%) as compared to females (33.33%). Sosale A et al [20] studied 4600 (males 67%, females 33%) newly diagnosed patients with T2D, majority were from the age group 41-50 years (40%).

In present study diabetic retinopathy was noted in 15 patients, divided as mild non proliferative diabetic retinopathy (66.66%), Moderate non proliferative diabetic retinopathy (20%), Severe non proliferative diabetic retinopathy (6.66%) and proliferative diabetic retinopathy (PDR) (6.66%). Macular oedema was noted in 4 patients. 60% of them had mild macular oedema while 20% each had moderate and severe macular oedema. Hao Z et al [21] enrolled 947 patients in their study and were divided into two groups according to whether they were diagnosed with DR. There was no statistically significant difference between the two groups in sex, age, hypertension, DM diagnosed age, family history of diabetes, drinking history and HbA1c. BMI was significantly higher in DR patients. newly diagnosed T2DM subjects, DR is associated with reduced beta-cell responsiveness, resulting from beta-cell failure rather than insulin resistance, leading to fasting and postprandial hyperglycaemia and hypoinsulinemia. [22] The most effective way of preventing the risk of vision loss from diabetes mellitus is patient education about the need for screening for retinopathy even in the absence of any visual complaints. Therefore, early screening is strongly recommended for all newly diagnosed T2DM patients

Conclusion

Screening for diabetic retinopathy is important for newly diagnosed diabetic patients. A systematic screening program in the community is needed for early detection and to reduce blindness in diabetic patients.

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